

TECHNICAL REPORT

D6.1: Report 1 on measures to create innovation eco- system around ANGIE technology

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Abstract	This deliverable report presents the mapping of the existing innovation in localized targeted drug delivery across the EU. It covers: a) the identification of active technology- and entrepreneurship meet-up groups, b) we pinpointed the innovation and entrepreneurship organizations that currently running programs in EU, c) the identification of main angel investors and venture capitalists that are active in Europe, d) we discovered journalists and news outlets that cover innovation and startup related subjects in Europe, e) the tracking of successful startups currently functioning in Europe, and f) we listed education institutions operating in Europe in the area of localized targeted drug delivery.
Keywords	Innovation; eco-system;

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PROJECT CONSORTIUM

Participant No.	Participant organisation name	Short name	Country
1. (Coordinator)	Swiss Federal Institute of Technology Zürich	ETH	Switzerland
2.	University of Würzburg	UoW	Germany
3.	University of Barcelona	UoB	Spain
4.	University of Crete	UoC	Greece
5.	Stroke Alliance for Europe (SAFE)	SAFE	Pan-European
6.	Experian	EXP	Portugal
7.	Magnebotix	MGBX	Switzerland
8.	Discovery Foundation	DF	Greece
9.	Verhaert	VERT	Belgium

1. INTRODUCTION

This deliverable documents activities that are performed in Work Package (WP) 6 “Create an innovation eco-system around the ANGIE technology to foster its take-up in the clinical environments”. The WP6 objectives include:

- Mapping the existing innovation in localized targeted drug delivery across the EU
- Creating a network of people with similar views and goals
- Reaching out to European and Local Governments.
- Developing online courses on ANGIE technology.
- Organising technical workshops on implementation and operation of ANGIE.
- Organising idea competitions

The purpose of this document is to report the measures taken in mapping the existing innovation in localized targeted drug delivery across the EU.

1.1. Scope

The present document is the Deliverable 6.1 “D6.1: Report 1 on measures to create innovation eco- system around ANGIE technology” (henceforth referred to as D6.1). The main objective of D6.1 is to map the existing innovation in localized targeted drug delivery across the EU. The first step to build our innovation eco-system was to become acquainted with all of the innovation and entrepreneurial activity happening around Europe. This will be key for enlarging the eco-system and organizing it to be attractive for all relevant stakeholders, especially given the infrastructure that will be developed to facilitate the development of the ecosystem. We used a 6-step process to map the existing innovation in the EU:

- identifying active -related meet-up groups;
- pinpointing innovation and entrepreneurship organizations like the startup weekends, tech conferences, etc. that are currently running programs in Europe;
- identifying the main angel investors and venture capitalists that are active in Europe;
- discovering journalists and news outlets that cover innovation- and startup related subjects in Europe;
- tracking successful startups currently functioning in Europe and using them as case studies;
- listing technology-related colleges, universities, and other education institutions operating in Europe in the area of localized targeted drug delivery.

1.2. Audience

This document (D6.1) is available to the public and the European Commission.

2. TECHNOLOGY AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP MEET-UP GROUPS

The first step in this process was to identify technology and entrepreneurship meetup groups in EU. These groups offer a variety of networking opportunities to connect with people who are working in related fields to your own, to promote and scale your business through genuine connections and to attend online networking, educational and entrepreneurship events.

Meetup.com is one of the most effective services used to organize online groups that help persons to host in-person and online events for people having similar interests. Through this platform we identified the below technology and entrepreneurship meet-up groups.

2.1. STEM 4 Health Berlin, Berlin, Germany, 5296 members

This meetup group aims to connect digital health startups, biotech startups, students, developers, technologists, scientists, biologists, bioinformaticians, data analysts, business intelligence analysts, designers, social media networkers, freelancers, established companies, institutes or organizations, venture capitalists, entrepreneurs, essentially anyone interested in life sciences, healthcare technologies and related businesses, with stakeholders in the healthcare system.

Meetup link: <https://www.meetup.com/STEM4health-Berlin/>

2.2. SingularityU Benelux, Eindhoven, Netherlands, 2.208 members

SingularityU Benelux provides educational programs and events to help the Benelux community understand cutting-edge technologies to positively impact billions of people. These technologies are Artificial Intelligence, Robotics, Nanotechnology, Biotechnology, Neuroscience, Sensors, 3D printers and Energy & Environmental Systems.

Meetup link: <https://www.meetup.com/SingularityUBenelux/>

2.3. Paris Healthcare Innovation Meetup, Paris, France, 1480 members

This group is for anyone interested in health, e-health, innovation, education, training and those who want to come together to share ideas worth spreading. All types of public and speakers are welcome, doctors, health professionals, entrepreneurs, start-ups, medical laboratories, students and doctors to join their group to meet and discuss regularly.

Meetup link: <https://www.meetup.com/Paris-Healthcare-Innovation-Meetup/>

2.4. Hacking Health Berlin, Berlin, Germany, 1.299 members

Hacking Health is designed to improve healthcare by inviting technology creators and healthcare professionals to collaborate on realistic, human-centric solutions to front-line problems. They have partnered with organizations like the Berlin Institute of Health, Data Natives, EIT Health, Fraunhofer Venture and the German Ministry of Health to host and support hackathons in Germany and throughout Europe.

Meetup link: <https://www.meetup.com/Hacking-Health-Berlin/>

2.5. Artificial Intelligence for Medical Technology, Amsterdam, Netherlands, 1.129 members

The healthcare industry stands out from other industries in many ways. The potential value of data-driven applications is by far more evident than in any other industry, and the amounts and diversity of medical data is abundant. Yet, the pace of innovation is slow, which is unfortunate in the context of the rapid advancements in the fields of computing and artificial intelligence. This group's mission is to accelerate innovation in data-driven healthcare by bringing together healthcare professionals, data specialists, and general enthusiasts.

Meetup link: <https://www.meetup.com/Artificial-Intelligence-for-Medical-Technology/>

2.6. Startup-Sprechstunde // Pfizer Healthcare Hub Berlin, Berlin, Germany, 1218 members

The Pfizer Healthcare Hub organizes the “Start-up Consultation Hours” – open for startups and everyone else interested in the Digital Health sector in order to listen and ask questions related to a specific topic. Pfizer's experts give insights from the pharmaceutical industry and external experts explain complex topics. From very specific event topics like the “German Drug Advertising Act” to hot topics such as “IoT in Healthcare” – everyone is welcome to come, ask and connect with their team and other healthcare innovators and entrepreneurs during the subsequent networking.

Meetup link: <https://www.meetup.com/startup-sprechstunde/>

2.7. STEM 4 Health & AgTech Milano, Milano, Italy, 867 members

This meet-up group aims to connect digital health startups, biotech startups, students, developers, technologists, scientists, biologists, bioinformatics, data analysts, business intelligence analysts, designers, social media networkers, freelancers, established companies, institutes or organisations, venture capitalists, entrepreneurs, essentially anyone interested in life sciences, healthcare technologies and related business, with stakeholders in the healthcare system.

Meetup link: <https://www.meetup.com/STEM-4-Health-AgTech-Milano/>

2.8. Medtec Meetups - Medical Technology and Innovation, London, United Kingdom, 322 members

This group aims to understand and explore the challenges for medical technology developers, clinical researchers and start-up entrepreneurs surrounding: R&D, design, manufacturing processes, regulation to help you take a fresh look at your own projects. Medtec meetups will deliver educational insights on important IP and legal considerations, routes to secure the critical funding, setting up an effective distribution system and the best strategies for international expansion. Meetup link: <https://www.meetup.com/MEDTEC-Meetups/>

2.9. Biomedical Engineering Group Twente, Enschede, Netherlands, 119 members

Biomedical Engineering Group Twente is a scientific community, which refers to students, researchers, and professionals interested to contribute to biomedical engineering research and development. Their events enable knowledge sharing and promote updates of future research directions, as well as connection and networking with colleagues.

Meetup link: <https://www.meetup.com/BioEngTwente/>

2.10. Groupe Meetup Start-up & Medtech, Paris, France, 56 members

This group is dedicated to Medtech. For people that are interested in innovation, entrepreneurship, training on new health technologies.

Meetup link: <https://www.meetup.com/StartupMedtech/>

3. INNOVATION AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP ORGANIZATIONS THAT ARE CURRENTLY RUNNING PROGRAMS IN EUROPE

The second step in the process of mapping the existing innovation in localized targeted drug delivery across the EU was to pinpoint innovation and entrepreneurship organizations like the startup weekends, tech conferences, etc. that are currently running programs in Europe. Through these programs entrepreneurs can share their projects and may attract potential investors, build their network and leverage

their skills. These programs are described in detail in the following subsections and are mapped in Figure 1.

3.1. Techstars Startup Weekend

Techstars Startup Weekend is a 3-day event during which groups of developers, business managers, startup enthusiasts, marketing experts, graphic artists and more pitch ideas for new startup companies, form teams around those ideas, and work to develop a working prototype, demo, or presentation by Sunday evening. Startup Weekend has grown into an organization with a global presence. As of December 2016, Startup Weekend has reached 135 countries, involving over 210,000 entrepreneurs. Upon its 2015 acquisition, Startup Weekend, alongside Startup Week and StartupDigest, became one of the Techstars family of startup programs.¹

3.2. Startupbootcamp

Startupbootcamp supports early-stage tech founders to rapidly scale their companies by providing direct access to an international network of the most relevant mentors, partners, and investors in their industry. With programs in major startup hubs including London, New York, Singapore, Berlin, Amsterdam, and many others, they provide both a global reach and industry-focus to our portfolio companies. By holding events in more than 100 cities each year they support the world's most talented founders with hands-on mentorship and access to key industry connections, as well as take part in all the major technology and industry conferences around the globe. Each Startupbootcamp program is tailor-made to deliver incredible value in a compact timeframe.²

3.3. StartupINVEST

StartupINVEST is the leading Swiss financing platform connecting Startups, Investors and Corporate industry leaders worldwide. Their mission is to foster innovation by facilitating the dialogue between high-tech curated startups, investors, industry partners and universities. To facilitate this, Startup INVEST organizes high-valuable events such as Startup days, Venture days, IPO days where participating startups get access to a vast members network, industry leaders and capital to support them during the foundation and growth phase of the companies in Switzerland and its expansion abroad.³

3.4. The Founder Institute

The Founder Institute is an American business incubator, entrepreneur training and startup launch program that was founded in Palo Alto, California in 2009. Although based in Silicon Valley, The Founder Institute maintains chapters in over 180 cities and more than 65 nations. It offers a four-month part-time program for new and early-stage entrepreneurs that helps them develop their business ideas and form a company. Among the key requirements for graduation is the creation of a fully operational company by the end of the four-month program.⁴

¹ <https://www.techstars.com>

² <https://www.startupbootcamp.org>

³ <http://www.startupinvest.ch>

⁴ <https://fi.co>

3.5. StartupBus

StartupBus is a tech entrepreneurship boot camp and global championship on wheels. StartupBus is an annual technological startup competition and entrepreneurship boot camp, described as a Hackathon, created by Elias Bizannes in February 2010. The competition is held across a 3-day bus ride where contestants or "buspreneurs" compete to conceive the best technology startup. The competition seeks to attract young top talents to compete, to search for the most innovative startup conceived by the groups, where the winners are determined by a panel of judges. StartupBus receives an extensive online media coverage through platforms such as BBC News, CNN and technology blogs and news sites such as The Next Web, VentureBeat, WIRED and TechCrunch.⁵

3.6. TechChill Foundation

TechChill Foundation is a non-profit organization with an aim to help Latvian and Baltic startups succeed in the world. They invite the best people from different fields to visit Riga for TechChill conference to promote Latvian and Baltic companies and ecosystems. Also, they organize various smaller events during the year to boost the startup ecosystem from different angles –attract the next leaders and founders via our student events, we help startups to attract the best talent, we host matchmaking as well as networking events. The main event of the year is the TechChill conference where they bring together 2000+ attendees, including the fastest-growing startups, most innovative corporations, investors active in the region and talented tech enthusiasts. Day 1 is a full day full of Workshops, Demo Days, Investor Day, Media and more events, followed by two-day agenda at TechChill main venue featuring 90+ speakers on two stages, Roundtable discussions, Startup Expo, Business Expo, Matchmaking area for the 1100+ startup & investor meetings and side events.⁶

3.7. GIANT Health

GIANT Health is a rapidly expanding global community (over 150,000 people) of everyone involved in healthcare innovation. The GIANT (Global Innovation and New Technology) Health Event is an innovation conference with immersive workshops and Beanstalks. Their vision is to improve the health and well-being of people around the world, by promoting healthcare innovation and supporting health-tech entrepreneurs. At the European Health Tech Week they bring together health-tech innovators, investors, doctors, hospital leaders from the world's largest pharma companies.⁷

3.8. Wolves Summit

Wolves Summit is one of the biggest networking business Tech conferences in Europe. It is a place for Startups, Investors, Corporates and Executives, where innovation meets business and capital. We connect angel investors, VC funds, tech talent, and corporations with the most promising startups in the CEE region to help ambitious founders scale and foster international economic growth. In the last five years they have adjusted the Wolves Match tool to facilitate strategic connections and strengthen ties between countries, expand startup ecosystems and grow opportunities for entrepreneurs. Every edition attracts more than 2500 participants from 80 countries providing 100+ hours of immersive educational content, keynotes and startup pitches.⁸

⁵ <https://startupbus.com/europe>

⁶ <https://techchill.co>

⁷ <https://www.giant.health>

⁸ <https://www.wolvessummit.com>

3.9. TOA is a community for knowledge exchange and collaboration

TOA is a community for knowledge exchange and collaboration. Their mission is to help people and organisations become futureproof. They connect, grow and inspire technology professionals through media, experiences and educational programs. The TOA Berlin event, their cohort-based learning program TOA Klub and our other virtual formats are delivered all year round.⁹

3.10. Tech Tour

Tech Tour, founded in Geneva in 1998, is an independent organisation committed to the development of emerging technology companies in Europe. Composed of key contributors to the high-tech industry and recognising the extraordinary competence, entrepreneurship and dynamism that can be found throughout the European hi-tech industry, the organisation aims to create synergies between, on the one hand, a selection of European start-up companies wishing to develop on the international level and, on the other, a network of leading figures from the world of high technology – industrialists, entrepreneurs, service-providers, players on the political and economic scene. The role of Tech Tour is to serve as the overall supervisor and coordinator for all events throughout Europe, while the task of organising events in each individual region are entrusted to a group of local volunteers designated by Tech Tour. In this way, a Europe-wide network has been created to stimulate exchanges of ideas and to promote young, dynamic companies.¹⁰

3.11. Hyphen Projects

Hyphen Projects is a private company that designs, develops and delivers conferences, summits, career events and courses for the Life Sciences sector. Innovation for Health conference provides a unique opportunity to meet leading innovators, to catch up on the latest trends, to present cutting-edge innovations and to engage leaders and decision makers in Life Sciences & Health. The conference brings top-notch speakers to the stage, displays high impact innovations, highlights best practices and demonstrates inspiring developments in healthcare. This is the meeting place where more than 900 bright minds from across Life Sciences and Health are united on the same day, where stakeholders in health and care, from bench to bedside, from start-up to multinational, with ideas and with funding, come together to strengthen existing contacts, to expand their networks, to establish collaborations, to jointly shape the future of healthcare.¹¹

3.12. MedFIT

Steered by a prestigious Committee, the MedFIT conference programme brings together bright minds to discuss the latest trends in MedTech, diagnostic and digital health, to debate on innovation-driven topics, to foster learning and provoke conversations that matter. International experts will address current industry issues related to collaboration, financing, market access and regulation as well as MedTech digitalisation. MedFIT is organised annually and alternates between Grenoble, Strasbourg, and Lille.¹²

⁹ <https://toa.berlin>

¹⁰ <https://techtour.com>

¹¹ <https://www.hyphenprojects.nl/i4h>

¹² <https://www.medfit-event.com>

3.13. WHINN

WHINN is an international life science and health tech conference organized as a festival including events, exhibition, match making and networking activities, all within health and innovation. WHINN has national and international partners operating within life science and health tech. In addition to talks, events and activities, they offer side events which feature state-of-the-art-technology in use; fascinating test laboratories where tomorrow's health technology is being developed, as well as inspirational company visits.¹³

3.14. European Health Forum Gastein

The European Health Forum Gastein is an independent, non-partisan organisation, founded in 1998 as a European health policy platform, which has since grown far beyond traditional health policy spaces. They aim to provide a neutral and inclusive platform for the discussion and advancement of health, solidarity and equity in the EU and beyond, and our founding principle is the equal representation of all stakeholders. The EHFG has developed into a key platform for health policy exchange, bringing together stakeholders and decision-makers from the public and private sector, civil society, and science and academia, who together form the four pillars of the EHFG with their specific perspectives and knowledge. Up to 900 leading experts, decision-makers and community members participate in the annual conference and take part in additional EHFG events and projects.¹⁴

3.15. EIT Health

EIT Health was established in 2015, as a knowledge and innovation community of the European Institute of Innovation and Technology. The idea behind the EIT KICs is that innovation flourishes best when the right people are brought together to share expertise. EIT Health organises Bootcamps where you learn how to develop your start-up to its full potential.¹⁵

¹³ <https://com.whinn.dk>

¹⁴ <https://www.ehfg.org/about-us/ehfg>

¹⁵ <https://eithealth.eu>

Figure 1 | Map pinpointing the locations of entrepreneurship programs in the EU.

Icon	Point Name	Address	Icon	Point Name	Address
	EIT Health	Munich Bavaria Germany		Startup Bus	Greece Greece
	EIT Health	London England United Kingdom		Startupbootcamp	France France
	EIT Health	Stockholm Stockholm County Sweden		Startupbootcamp	United Kingdom United Kingdom
	EIT Health	Barcelona Catalonia Spain		Startupbootcamp	Amsterdam North Holland Netherlands
	European Health Forum Gastein	Bad Gastein Sankt Johann im Pongau, Salzburg Austria		Startupbootcamp	Berlin Germany
	GIANT Health	Liverpool Merseyside, England United Kingdom		TechChill Foundation	Rome Latium Italy
	GIANT Health	Paris Ile-de-France France		TechChill Foundation	Estonia Estonia
	GIANT Health	Berlin Germany		TechChill Foundation	Latvia Latvia
	GIANT Health	Barcelona Catalonia Spain		Techstars Startup Weekend	Lithuania Lithuania
	GIANT Health	Stockholm Stockholm County Sweden		Techstars Startup Weekend	Bucharest Romania
	Hyphen Project	Hilversum North Holland Netherlands		Techstars Startup Weekend	Amsterdam-Centrum Amsterdam Netherlands
	MedFIT	Grenoble Isère, Auvergne-Rhone-Alpes France		Techstars Startup Weekend	Berlin Germany
	Startup Bus	France France		Techstars Startup Weekend	Munich Bavaria Germany
	Startup Bus	Amsterdam North Holland Netherlands		Techstars Startup Weekend	Athens Attiki Greece
	Startup Bus	Germany Germany		The Founder Institute	London England United Kingdom
	Startup Bus	Spain		The Founder Institute	Belgium Belgium
	Startup Bus	United Kingdom United Kingdom		The Founder Institute	Sofia-City Bulgaria
	Startup Bus	Estonia Estonia		The Founder Institute	Croatia Croatia
	Startup Bus	Italy Italy		The Founder Institute	Spain Spain
	Startup Bus	Switzerland Switzerland		The Founder Institute	France France
					Hungary Hungary

4. ANGEL INVESTORS AND VENTURE CAPITALISTS

The third step in the process of mapping the existing innovation in localized targeted drug delivery across the EU was to identify the main angel investors and venture capitalists that are active in Europe. Angels' investors and Venture Capitalists, which are often experts in the industry, provide both financing and managerial experience in high potential (early-stage) start-up companies in return for an equity stake. These investors bring a wealth of experience and share their knowledge at critical stages to help startups through the initial stages, and they are described in detail in the following subsections and are mapped in Figure 2.

4.1. European Trade Association for Business Angels, Brussels, Belgium

The European Trade Association for Business Angels (EBAN), Seed Funds and Early-Stage Market Players represents the early-stage investor community in Europe, including business angel networks and angel investors. EBAN is the pan-European representative for the early-stage investor community gathering over 150 member organizations in more than 50 countries today. Established in 1999 by a group of pioneer angel networks in Europe with the collaboration of the European Commission and EURADA, EBAN represents a sector estimated to invest 11.4 billion Euros a year and playing a vital role in Europe's future, notably in the funding of SMEs. EBAN fuels Europe's growth through the creation of wealth and jobs.¹⁶

4.2. Business Angels Europe, Brussels, Belgium

Business Angels Europe (BAE) is the European Confederation of Angel Investing, representing the European Business Angels' Federations and Trade associations in Europe. BAE brings together the most active and developed countries operating in the angel market in Europe.¹⁷

4.3. SeedBlink, Bucarest, Romania

SeedBlink is the fastest growing investing platform specialized in sourcing, vetting, financing, and scaling European tech start-ups. Their vision is to shape Europe's tech future by creating an investment platform that has the reach of crowdfunding, the flexibility of angel investors, and the structure of venture capital. With the input of their stellar team and an array of trusted partners experienced in entrepreneurship, banking investment, VC/Angels, they lower barriers to access pre-vetted start-up investments.¹⁸

4.4. Mines Alès Angels, Ales, France

Mines Alès Angels is an angel network from France. It helps to connect business angels and entrepreneurs in order to facilitate business creation through appropriate and efficient support. Its desire is to support the creation of innovative companies, with high technological potential, by supporting women and men from the first stages of creation. Their mission is to connect business angels and entrepreneurs in order to facilitate business creation through appropriate and efficient support.¹⁹

¹⁶ www.eban.org

¹⁷ www.businessangelseurope.com

¹⁸ www.seedblink.com

¹⁹ <https://mines-ales-angels.com>

4.5. COREangels, Lisbon, Portugal

COREangels is a network for people with a passion for helping entrepreneurs launch innovative businesses by professionally investing as Business Angel Investors. Business Angels Investing on Impact Driven Projects through Angel groups led by committed people who love entrepreneurship. Always on the entrepreneur side, they address markets, raise capital and achieve exits.²⁰

4.6. AngelsDen, London, United Kingdom

AngelsDen is a tech-powered investment platform that connects a network of more than 19,000 investors with early-stage technology startups. They help startups to find suitable investors. Throughout their history, they have raised funding for over 270 startups, that are now collectively valued at \$1.5B.²¹

4.7. Earlybird Venture Capital, Berlin, Germany

Earlybird Venture Capital, is among the most experienced venture investors in Europe. The VC fund offers its portfolio companies not only financial resources but also strategic and operational support and access to an international network and capital markets. Earlybird Venture Capital has grown to three autonomous, dedicated and specialized teams, focusing on different geographies and sectors. The Digital West Fund focuses primarily on early stage digital technology opportunities in GSA, Nordics, UK, Benelux, France and Southern Europe, while the Digital East Fund is focused on early stage ICT investment opportunities in Eastern Europe and Turkey, being the leading tech VC in this region. The Health Fund focuses on early and later stage opportunities in digital health, medical devices, diagnostics, enabling technologies and biopharma across Europe. With EUR 1.5 billion under management, eight IPOs and 30 trade sales, Earlybird is one of the most successful venture capital firms in Europe.²²

4.8. Finch Capital, Amsterdam, Netherlands

Finch Capital funds and supports exceptional entrepreneurs creating products that will shape the future of finance. Finch is investing in companies that have solutions to real problems and help make them better, more sustainable, and scalable. Finch Capital is a series A/B investor in high-growth financial technologies companies run by exceptional entrepreneurs. Their mission is to fund and support the best entrepreneurs creating products that will shape the future of finance. They have developed extensive experience in building businesses, expanding into different countries, building partnerships, dealing with regulators and exiting and buying companies.²³

4.9. Versant Ventures, Basel, Switzerland

Versant Ventures is a leading investor in the biotechnology, medical devices and health care space, helping exceptional entrepreneurs with great ideas make a difference in the global healthcare marketplace. The firm invests in projects across the healthcare sector and at various stages of company development, but focuses on firms developing novel therapeutics. Versant's website boasts that since its inception in 1999, it has helped more than 65 companies achieve successful acquisitions or IPOs. Versant's Discovery Engines

²⁰ <https://www.coreangels.com>

²¹ www.angelsden.com

²² <https://earlybird.com>

²³ <https://www.finchcapital.com>

comprise in-house teams of multi-disciplinary scientists working in state-of-the-art laboratory facilities to enable the launch of novel biotechnology companies with academic founders.²⁴

4.10. HV Holtzbrinck Ventures GmbH, Berlin, Germany

HV Holtzbrinck Ventures GmbH invests early in companies that are developing exceptional products. The VC fund has enabled hundreds of entrepreneurs, creating an ecosystem for companies to connect and thrive together. HV co-invests with a set of top international business angels and investors. In the last 20 years, the fund has backed 200 companies and enabled the creation of more than 100 thousand jobs across all sectors of the industry.²⁵

4.11. Life Sciences Partners, Amsterdam, The Netherlands

Life Sciences Partners (LSP) is one of Europe's largest and most experienced healthcare investment firms. With a track record going back more than 30 years, they have built up an investment house that is dedicated to only one task: seeking, nurturing and growing healthcare investment opportunities with the potential to have a positive impact on society.²⁶

4.12. Forbion Capital Partners, Amsterdam, The Netherlands

Forbion is a leading European venture capital firm that helps companies bridge research and development through the team's expertise in drug development and company building. Forbion is a signatory to the United Nations Principles for Responsible Investment further demonstrating its philosophy that investments in companies should positively impact the health and well-being of patients.

4.13. Abingworth, London, United Kingdom

With offices in the world's key biotech centres, Abingworth supports entrepreneurs in both the US and Europe. Their venture funds invest across our broad strategic areas of venture capital, clinical co-development, VIPes and public markets. They focus primarily on private companies but invest a percentage of their value in public companies as well.²⁷

4.14. Balderton Capital, London, United Kingdom

Balderton Capital is a venture capital firm focused exclusively on backing European-founded startups. They invest in companies with the potential to disrupt huge industries, and the ambition to scale globally. Balderton brings deep experience, unrivalled professional, and personal network to support companies they invest in from start to exit.²⁸

4.15. Change Ventures, Tallin, Estonia

Change Ventures enables ambitious Baltic founders with the grit to succeed to build global, scalable businesses. With 45 years of combined experience, the fund's partners aim to provide a founder-friendly, fast, and efficient investment process. Change Ventures helps companies after investment by getting to

²⁴ <https://www.versantventures.com>

²⁵ <https://www.hvcapital.com>

²⁶ <https://www.lspvc.com>

²⁷ <https://www.abingworth.com>

²⁸ <https://www.balderton.com>

product-market fit and scaling the business with a personal network of over 450 follow-on and co-investors around the globe.²⁹

Figure 2 | Map pinpointing the locations of Angel investors and Capital Ventures across the EU.

5. MEDIA AND JOURNALISTS

The fourth step in the process of mapping the existing innovation in localized targeted drug delivery across the EU was to discover journalists and news outlets that cover innovation- and startup related subjects in Europe. These are described in detail in the following subsections.

5.1. Sifted

Sifted is a new-media site for Europe's innovators and entrepreneurs. Their goal is to give a voice to a remarkable new generation of European entrepreneurs determined to improve the world. With a team of 11 journalists across the region, they provide the most insightful coverage of Europe's fast-evolving startup world. Website: <https://sifted.eu>, Innovation editor: Majja Palmer

²⁹ <https://www.changeventures.com>

5.2. StartupReporter

StartupReporter, is a blog dedicated to obsessively profiling and reviewing new Internet products and companies. In addition to covering new companies, StartupReporter speaks about existing companies that are making an impact (commercial and/or cultural) on the startup ecosystem in Europe.³⁰

5.3. CoFounder

CoFounder Magazine is quarterly print magazine for the European start-up community, writing about the journey of successful startups, stories of Entrepreneurs who failed or excelled, tips Startups and basically any news that caters to the Startup Industry.³¹ Journalist: Tarmo Virki.

5.4. Deutsche startups

The online magazine Deutsche startups has been providing information about new trends from the internet start-up scene since 2007. Interviews, portraits of individual startups and founders as well as market overviews on interesting segments complement the daily rush of news.³² Co-founder and editor in chief Alexander Hüsing.

5.5. The Next Web

The Next Web (TNW) is a technology-focused media company that manages several initiatives focused on international technology news, business, and culture. The Next Web expands its global presence on and off its website through content syndication, with events that bring the tech-ecosystem together, and the addition of new channels and online services that come out of The Next Web Labs. Its online publication has editions in Europe, Latin America, and North America. The Next Web Events organizes tech conferences that enable the international tech community to meet, do business, and learn about the latest trends in web and mobile.³³ Editor in Chief: Alejandro Tauber.

5.6. Tech.eu

Tech.eu offers a curated selection of stories on European startups, scale-ups, venture capital, policy and more, through a combination of a unique online magazine, industry newsletters, research reports, a podcast, job platform and event calendar.³⁴ Technology journalist: Robin Wauters.

5.7. Barcinno

Barcinno is a collaborative platform sharing the news, knowledge and events of Barcelona's startup, tech and innovation communities. Barcinno is a unique channel for Barcelona's rapidly growing entrepreneurial community to expand their presence locally as well as internationally.³⁵ Contributing Editor: Stewart Masters.

³⁰ <https://www.startupreporter.eu>

³¹ <https://www.cofmag.com/about-cofounder>

³² <https://www.deutsche-startups.de>

³³ <https://thenextweb.com/eu>

³⁴ <https://tech.eu>

³⁵ <http://www.barcinno.com>

5.8. Silicon Canals

Silicon Canals is a leading technology media source for the Benelux and wider Europe. They cover news, knowledge, and insights from the European technology and startup ecosystem, providing a growing number of startups CEOs, technology scale-up founders, angel investors, venture capitalists, innovation managers, and other interested parties from the tech and startup community with invaluable and indispensable information.³⁶ Editor in chief: Rahul Raj.

5.9. EU-Startups

EU-Startups is an online publication with a focus on startups in Europe. They write about internet and tech startups out of Europe and provide their readers with data-driven analysis, interviews and startup-related news. They also publish other kinds of news out of the tech-space that has a commercial or cultural impact on startups in Europe.³⁷ Head of Content: Charlotte Tucker.

5.10. Wired

Wired is a magazine that reports on the effects of science and technology. It covers a broad range of topics including design, architecture, culture, the economy, politics and philosophy. They cover fields from the latest in science and technology to the big stories in business and culture.³⁸ Writer and editor: Craig Grannell.

5.11. Arctic Startup

Arctic Startup is a new media and events company from Finland, covering startups from Scandinavia and the Baltics. They encourage entrepreneurship and support businesses that have meaning and entrepreneurs that bush boundaries of what they'd thought possible.³⁹ Editor in Chief: Jan Ameri.

5.12. Medical Technology

Medical Technology is a digital magazine for the medical device industry. This magazine brings together the latest news, market insights and technological developments from the industry. Looking at all areas of healthcare, from prevention and monitoring to diagnosis and treatment, they keep an eye on new research and innovation in materials, electronics, devices, manufacturing technologies.⁴⁰ <https://www.medicaldevice-network.com/> Reporter: Chloe Kent.

5.13. Startups

Startups Magazine is a bi-monthly print and digital publication created to champion technology startups with all aspects of their entrepreneurial journeys, helping them connect the dots from funding to founder wellbeing. Startups Magazine launched has built a loyal and talented following ranging from tech startups, engineers, investors, growth hackers, accelerators, marketing whizzes, aspiring innovators and many more.⁴¹ Editor: Anna Flockett.

³⁶ <https://siliconcanals.com>

³⁷ <https://www.eu-startups.com>

³⁸ <https://www.wired.co.uk>

³⁹ <https://arcticstartup.com>

⁴⁰ <https://www.medicaldevice-network.com>

⁴¹ <https://startupsmagazine.co.uk>

6. SUCCESSFUL STARTUPS CURRENTLY FUNCTIONING IN EUROPE

The fifth step in the process of mapping the existing innovation in localized targeted drug delivery across the EU was to track successful medtech startups that currently are functioning in Europe. These are described in detail in the following subsections.

6.1. KRY

KRY company provides a platform on which users can connect with qualified healthcare professionals, nurses, doctors, and psychologists via their smartphone or tablet. Appointments over video-chat are available for immediate sessions via a drop-in service or for future sessions, through which health professionals diagnose patients and prescribe medication when appropriate. It is backed by some of Europe's savviest tech investors including Index Ventures and Accel – both of which contributed to its €140 million (\$155 million) Series C fundraise in January 2020.⁴² KRY operates in Sweden, Norway and Germany, while it trades under the brand name 'LIVI' in the UK and France.⁴³

6.2. MindMaze

Founded in 2012, MindMaze is a global leader in brain technology with a mission to accelerate humanity's ability to recover, learn and adapt. With over a decade of work at the intersection of neuroscience, biosensing, engineering, mixed reality and artificial intelligence, they have enhanced the recovery potential of patients with neurological diseases. They became McLaren Racing's Formula 1 technology partner and together developed MindDrive, a biosensing net to enhance safety and performance. MindMaze has raised a total of \$110.7M⁴² in funding over 8 rounds.⁴⁴

6.3. Atlantic Therapeutics

Atlantic Therapeutics focus is on the treatment of incontinence, sexual health dysfunctions and other associated disorders, and are on a mission to help people suffering globally by strengthening the muscles and modulating the nerves of the pelvic floor. They develop and manufacture medical device-quality pelvic floor strengthening and nerve stimulation products, all backed by strong clinical evidence and subjected to controlled trials. Healthcare professionals across the world rely on Atlantic Therapeutics to improve thousands of lives every year. Atlantic Therapeutics has raised a total of \$48.8M⁴² in funding over 6 rounds.⁴⁵

6.4. Qare

Qare is a platform that provides medical video consultation services. With over 12 specialities covered, Qare is the first telemedicine platform to offer an innovative and holistic health service to the French-speaking community based in London. Qare has raised a total of €26M⁴² in funding over 2 rounds.⁴⁶

6.5. Sensome

Sensome developed a revolutionary sensor technology that turns invasive medical devices into connected healthcare devices. The company's sensing technology combines impedance-based micro-sensors with

⁴² <https://www.crunchbase.com>

⁴³ <https://www.kry.se/en>

⁴⁴ <https://www.mindmaze.com>

⁴⁵ <https://atlantictherapeutics.com>

⁴⁶ <https://www.qare.fr>

machine learning algorithms to instantly identify biological tissues upon contact with an unequalled predictive reliability. Its first application is the Clotild® connected guidewire for the treatment of ischemic stroke. Sensome's sensor technology can be deployed in multiple other medical fields, such as interventional cardiology and oncology. Founded in 2014 and based in Massy, France Sensome has raised a total of \$18.9M⁴² in funding over 6 rounds.⁴⁷

6.6. ECG for Everybody

ECG for Everybody is an IOT based healthcare device designed to remotely monitor the heart for early diagnosis and post-hospital treatment screening. They have designed a mobile ECG sensing extender, mobile app and web platform to detect and document infrequent symptomatic arrhythmias or track post-myocardial infarction, enabling doctors to track the patient's health and fitness level. ECG for Everybody has raised a total of \$16.5K⁴² in funding over 2 rounds.⁴⁸

6.7. No Isolation

No Isolation is a Norwegian startup, founded in October 2015. Their mission is to reduce involuntary loneliness and social isolation by developing communication tools that help those affected. Their first product is AV1, the telepresence robot designed to allow children and young adults with long-term illness to participate in their social and educational lives. AV1 was launched in August 2016 and currently helps around 500 children across thirteen countries. Their second product is KOMP, the one-button screen designed to improve the communication between generations and family members, regardless of technological skills. Through KOMP, seniors can receive messages, photos and video calls. No Isolation has raised a total of \$10.6M⁴² in funding over 6 rounds.⁴⁹

6.8. Resistell

Resistell has proposed and developed a new approach to determine bacterial resistance to antibiotics, which significantly reduces time to results, and therefore benefits the patients and healthcare systems. Their proposal is an alternative to the current gold standard in antibiotic susceptibility testing. The method shortens the time needed for this test from days to hours, as it does not rely on bacterial growth, becoming a game-changer for everyone involved. Founded in 2018 and based in Muttenz, Switzerland, Resistell has raised a total of \$7.3M⁴² in funding over 8 rounds.⁵⁰

6.9. RTsafe

RTsafe was founded in 2014 by medical physics professors with considerable experience in the field of radiation oncology, aiming to address the issue of quality assurance in radiotherapy. RTsafe expanded rapidly and established collaborations with renowned hospitals and academic institutions thanks to the exceptional teamwork of its experienced scientists and software developers. RTsafe offers dosimetry services which incorporate phantoms built from real patient anatomical data by combining proven expertise in medical physics with highly accurate 3D printing technology. The company's vision is a world

⁴⁷ <https://www.sensome.com>

⁴⁸ <https://ecg4everybody.com>

⁴⁹ <https://www.noisolation.com/global>

⁵⁰ <https://resistell.com>

where every radiotherapy intervention is tested on a PseudoPatient before the real patient. RTsafe has raised a total of \$3.9M⁴² in funding over 7 rounds.⁵¹

6.10. Biotx.ai

Biotx.ai delivers predictive biomarkers as a basis for decision support in precision medicine. The company's platform provides an effective way to monitor individual responses to drug action and uses machine learning algorithms like artificial neural networks to stratify patients in clinical studies, enabling physicians to currently overcome unmet medical needs. The startup entered the capital market in 2017, receiving investments of € 2M in total.⁵²

6.11. CereGate

CereGate is focusing on developing new ways of interfacing with the human brain through the latest technology. Their mission is to provide patients with neurological disorders or sensory deficits, with new opportunities to adapt and improve their condition under their own power. Aiming to increase patient independence while improving quality of life, as well as the development of the system for new indications in stroke rehabilitation, neuroprosthetics, and computer/brain-interfacing. Founded in 2019 based in Munich, Germany, CereGate received a Seed capital investment by Heal Capital and High-Tech Grunderfonds. The parties agreed not to disclose any further details of the financing round.⁵³

7. EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS OPERATING IN EUROPE IN THE AREA OF LOCALIZED TARGETED DRUG DELIVERY

The sixth and last step in the process of mapping the existing innovation in localized targeted drug delivery across the EU was to list technology-related colleges, universities, and other education institutions operating in Europe in the area of localized targeted drug delivery. These are described in detail in the following subsections.

7.1. Utrecht Institute for Pharmaceutical Sciences

The Utrecht Institute for Pharmaceutical Sciences (UIPS) is the research institute of the Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences of the Faculty of Science of Utrecht University. The scientific research at UIPS focuses on processes around discovery, development, and use of drugs and medical nutrition using molecular and technological principles from the Natural and Life Sciences. The focus is shifting from small-molecule blockbusters to the high hanging fruit of peptides, proteins, nucleotides and even more advanced medical products like (stem) cells.⁵⁴

7.2. School of Pharmacy and Biomolecular Sciences, Liverpool John Moores University

The School of Pharmacy and Biomolecular Sciences, Liverpool John Moores University, brings together researchers from across chemistry, biomaterials, pharmaceuticals and biological sciences – taking a truly multidisciplinary approach to research. Their focus is towards the successful delivery of therapeutic agents

⁵¹ <https://rt-safe.com>

⁵² <https://biotx.ai>

⁵³ <https://ceregate.com>

⁵⁴ <https://www.uu.nl/en/research/utrecht-institute-for-pharmaceutical-sciences-uips>

in a controlled and targeted manner and the development of advanced delivery systems for a variety of applications. Formulation and drug delivery research is split into three themes that share a common aim of designing and formulating better drug delivery systems: Nanoformulation, Dosage form research and Pharmaceutical technology. In addition, the University offers a Drug Discovery, Development and Delivery MSc in association with industry leaders and promotes a critical awareness of the most recent advances in the field.⁵⁵

7.3. Pharmaceutical Technology and Biopharmacy Department, University of Medicine and Pharmacy “Iuliu Hațieganu” Cluj–Napoca

The research activity of Pharmaceutical Technology and Biopharmacy Department from the University of Medicine and Pharmacy “Iuliu Hațieganu” Cluj–Napoca (UMFC) is focused on developing innovative dosage forms with systemic, local and targeted drug delivery. To achieve targeted drug delivery at organ/cell level, micro and nanoparticulate pharmaceutical systems are developed. The drug development studies are performed in a structured and organized manner by using Design of Experiments (DoE), in order to determine the relationship between the formulation factors/process parameters and critical quality attributes of the dosage forms, according to the Quality by Design (QbD) approach.⁵⁶

7.4. Nanotechnology Lab LTFN, Physics Department, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki

The Nanotechnology Lab LTFN, Physics Department, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki (AUTH) has an experience of more than 25 years in Thin films Technology, fabrication of advanced nanomaterials and nanoparticles, developing/deploying in-situ and real-time optical metrology techniques, computational modeling and nanometrology tools. The mission of LTFN is to promote world-class research and best-practices in Nanotechnology, Organic Electronics, Nanomedicine and Nanometrology in order to address global challenges in Manufacturing, Energy, Lighting, Electronics, Photonics, IoT, Transportation, Health and Quality of Life, Agriculture, etc.⁵⁷

7.5. Institute for Molecules and Materials, Radboud University

The Institute for Molecules and Materials (IMM) is an interdisciplinary research institute in chemistry and physics at Radboud University. Its mission is to perform fundamental research to understand, design and control the functioning of molecules. The Systems Chemistry group finds its inspiration in natural materials and processes. Well-defined molecular systems with a high level of complexity are constructed, which find their potential application in the biomedical field. Within their group they have two main research topics such as: Smart Functional Nanomotors and Nanoreactors & Nanomedicine.⁵⁸

7.6. Leiden Academic Centre for Drug Research (LACDR), Science department, Leiden University

The Leiden Academic Centre for Drug Research (LACDR), Science department of Leiden University, is a centre of excellence for multidisciplinary research on drug discovery and development. Their research is focused in three divisions: Drug Discovery & Safety, BioTherapeutics and Systems Biomedicine and Pharmacology. At the LACDR we work at the leading edge of drug-design and fundamental research of

⁵⁵ <https://www.ljmu.ac.uk/about-us/faculties/faculty-of-science/school-of-pharmacy-and-biomolecular-sciences/research>

⁵⁶ <http://www.umfcluj.ro/en>

⁵⁷ <http://www.ltfn.gr>

⁵⁸ <https://www.ru.nl/systemschemistry/research>

new drugs, optimization of existing drugs, and personalised medicine. They offer Bachelor's and Master's programs in Bio-Pharmaceutical Sciences and the LACDR PhD program.⁵⁹

7.7. Newcastle University

The Newcastle University offers a 12-month a research-based course with a taught component on Drug Delivery and Nanomedicine. This course is about the effective design and development of modern medicines providing key research training and skills for a career in this area to meet the market demand in the global pharmaceutical sector.⁶⁰

7.8. Nanomedicines and Biomedical Engineering, Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Helsinki

The Nanomedicines and Biomedical Engineering, at the Faculty of Pharmacy, University of Helsinki, offers training in pharmaceutical nanotechnology at the B.Sc., M.Sc. and doctoral levels. Their research team makes the unique bridge between medical engineering, pharmaceutical nanotechnology and biomedical research by combining unique techniques, such as microfluidic glass technology, to help to build innovative nanomedicines/nanovectors and multidrug loading. To design and test the functionality and efficacy of these nanomedicines, we use state-of-the-art nanotheranostic technologies for personalized medicine, which allow the precisely engineering of materials at nanoscale to develop novel therapeutic formulations, including industrial scale-up validation, batch-to-batch reproducibility, and controllability of the nanomaterials' physicochemical properties for translation into the clinic.⁶¹

7.9. Department of Pharmacy, University of Patras

The Department of Pharmacy, University of Patras, offers the Nanomedicine for Drug Delivery (NANOMED) Master's degree, a 24-months training programme offering a high quality and multidisciplinary education in the emerging field of Nanomedicine. Four European Universities have brought together their expertise in Nanomedicine to create this unique and comprehensive training programme: Paris Descartes University (coordinator, France), Patras University (Greece), Pavia University (Italy) and Angers University (France).⁶²

7.10. Interdisciplinary Nanoscience Center (iNANO), Aarhus University

The Interdisciplinary Nanoscience Center (iNANO) at Aarhus University is a modern research and education center which was founded by Professor Flemming Besenbacher in 2002. Since then, iNANO has promoted research, education and knowledge transfer within nanoscience and nanotechnology with particular emphasis on collaboration across traditional disciplinary boundaries. Their mission is to conduct excellent interdisciplinary research in nanoscience and nanotechnology in collaboration with the strongest national and international research groups in this area and to play a key role in the education of the next generation of scientists in nanoscience at the BSc, MSc, PhD, and postdoctoral levels.⁶³

⁵⁹ <https://www.universiteitleiden.nl/en/science/drug-research>

⁶⁰ <https://www.ncl.ac.uk/postgraduate/courses/degrees/drug-delivery-nano-mres/#profile>

⁶¹ <https://www2.helsinki.fi/en/researchgroups/nanomedicines-and-biomedical-engineering>

⁶² <http://www.pharmacy.upatras.gr/index.php/en/studies/2019-11-14-06-55-38/2019-11-14-09-37-11/nanomed>

⁶³ <https://inano.au.dk>

7.11. Faculty of Science and Engineering, University of Groningen

The division of Nanomedicine & Drug Targeting organizes multiple teaching projects/courses in the curriculum of the bachelor programs Pharmaceutical Sciences, and Pharmacy as well as in the master programs Pharmacy, Medical Pharmaceutical Sciences, and in the topmaster Medical Pharmaceutical Drug Innovation in the Faculty of Natural Sciences. In addition, group members participate in courses in the Faculty of Medical Sciences as well as in the interfaculty curriculum "Life Sciences and Technology". The teaching program of the department deals with all aspects of drug transport and metabolism: absorption, distribution and excretion mechanisms, pharmacokinetic analysis, drug delivery and drug targeting technology, immunopharmacology/pharmacokinetics, gene and antisense delivery, pharmacokinetic modeling and software development, drug monitoring in relation to pharmacotherapy and drug interactions, pharmacokinetic/pharmacodynamic relationships, biological toxicology, as well as pharmacology and pharmacokinetics of anti-tumor agents and drug therapy in general.⁶⁴

7.12. Center for Biopharmaceuticals and Biobarriers in Drug Delivery, Faculty of Health and Medical Sciences, University of Copenhagen

The Department of Pharmacy is an internationally well-recognized research organization within pharmaceutical sciences, spanning research within drug delivery, pharmaceutical technology and formulation design, advanced drug analysis, and clinical and social pharmacy. The Center Biopharmaceuticals and Biobarriers in Drug Delivery aims to be recognized as an international excellence center, performing state-of-the-art research and creating innovative solutions within drug delivery of biopharmaceuticals. The scientific platform is built on integrated biophysical approaches, as well as novel opportunities in nanotechnology, application of advanced analytical methodologies, and representative biological models.⁶⁵

⁶⁴ <https://www.rug.nl/research/pharmacokinetics-toxicology-targeting/education>

⁶⁵ <https://biodelivery.ku.dk>